

Is Proximity Enough? Heat-Conditioned Walkability and Accessibility Equity in the 15-Minute City

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Abstract

The 15-minute city paradigm is commonly assessed under an implicit assumption of uniform walking conditions, overlooking how extreme heat may reduce the functional accessibility of daily services. This study develops a heat-conditioned accessibility framework to examine whether nominal proximity overstates meaningful walkability in climate-stressed urban environments. Using Shenzhen, China, as a case study, we integrate multi-source environmental, network, service, socioeconomic, and behavioural data, including ERA5-Land thermal conditions, MODIS land surface temperature, VIIRS nighttime lights, OpenStreetMap pedestrian networks and points of interest, and geotagged Weibo activity records. We compare baseline and heat-penalised accessibility across five categories of urban services, examine behavioural correspondence through high-heat versus reference-day activity patterns, and assess socioeconomic heterogeneity in heat-related accessibility loss. Preliminary results show that, under the medium penalty scenario, 13.44% of populated grid cells in 2023 and 12.65% in 2024 experience measurable service accessibility loss. Behavioural evidence indicates a consistent compression of midday activity and a corresponding increase in evening activity during high-heat conditions. Pooled equity models further reveal a significant interaction between heat exposure and socioeconomic status ($\beta = -0.0175$, $p = 0.0015$), indicating that heat-related accessibility degradation is not uniformly distributed across urban space. These findings suggest that proximity alone is insufficient for evaluating climate-resilient service access and provide a basis for future pedestrian-scale thermal accessibility research.

Keywords: 15-minute city, heat exposure, walkability, accessibility loss, environmental justice, urban resilience

Introduction

The 15-minute city has emerged as a prominent paradigm in sustainable urban planning, advocating that essential services should be reachable within a short walking or cycling time from

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3–6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

residents' homes (Moreno et al. 2021). In practice, however, most assessments of the 15-minute city rely on geometric distance, standard travel-time assumptions, or constant walking speeds. These approaches implicitly assume that the pedestrian environment is spatially uniform and climatically benign. Such an assumption becomes increasingly problematic under the growing threat of extreme heat in high-density cities, where outdoor mobility and walking comfort may vary substantially across space and time.

Existing research provides three important foundations for this study. First, high-temperature conditions can suppress outdoor mobility, alter travel timing, and affect route or activity choices (Jia et al. 2023, Zhang et al. 2022, Park et al. 2020). Second, accessibility to urban services is intrinsically uneven and strongly shaped by the spatial distribution of facilities and population demand (Neutens et al. 2012). Third, exposure to urban environmental stressors is often socially differentiated, raising concerns about climate-related inequalities in everyday access (Hsu et al. 2021). Yet these strands of evidence are rarely integrated into a single analytical framework for reassessing the 15-minute city under heat stress.

This short paper addresses three linked questions. First, how much service accessibility is lost when walking conditions are penalised under high-heat exposure? Second, do observed urban activity patterns show behavioural signals consistent with modelled heat-related accessibility contraction? Third, is heat-related accessibility loss unevenly associated with socioeconomic conditions? To answer these questions, we develop a multi-source geospatial workflow that combines environmental exposure modelling, network-based accessibility analysis, behavioural corroboration, and equity assessment. In the context of GeoAI-oriented urban analytics, the contribution lies in integrating heterogeneous geospatial and behavioural data to reveal climate-sensitive accessibility patterns that are not visible in conventional proximity-based evaluations.

Data and Methodology

Study Area and Data

The study area is Shenzhen, a subtropical and highly urbanised megacity in southern China. The analysis is conducted on a 1 km \times 1 km populated origin grid. The year 2023 serves as the primary analytical year, while 2024 is used as a robustness comparison.

Five types of data are integrated. First, ERA5-Land hourly meteorological data are used to construct the temporal component of high-heat exposure. Second, MODIS hot-season median composites of land surface temperature (LST) and Normalised Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) are used to derive local spatial thermal anomalies. Third, OpenStreetMap walkable road networks and points of interest (POIs) are used to calculate service accessibility across five facility groups: grocery, health, finance, food, and leisure. Fourth, VIIRS nighttime light intensity is used as a preliminary spatial proxy for socioeconomic status (SES) in the equity analysis. Fifth, full geotagged Weibo activity records are used for behavioural corroboration of high-heat accessibility patterns.

Analytical Framework Overview

The analytical workflow consists of three stages (*Figure 1*). The first stage constructs a heat-conditioned environmental exposure representation by combining city-wide temporal heat intensity with local spatial thermal anomalies. The second stage embeds this exposure information into network travel-time penalties and compares baseline versus heat-conditioned accessibility across service categories. The third stage evaluates whether modelled accessibility contraction is supported by observed behavioural patterns and whether the resulting losses are socioeconomically differentiated.

Figure 1: Analytical framework for heat-conditioned accessibility assessment, behavioural corroboration, and equity evaluation.

Temporal-Spatial Heat Exposure Signal

We construct a two-component heat exposure signal. The temporal component, denoted as H_t , is derived from ERA5-Land hourly daytime thermal conditions over local daytime hours. It represents the city-wide variation in high-heat intensity across days and is used to distinguish high-heat periods from reference conditions. In this short paper, H_t is interpreted as a mesoscale thermal stress signal rather than a direct pedestrian-scale thermal comfort metric.

The spatial component, denoted as S_i , captures intra-urban thermal anomaly. Following the established relationship between vegetation abundance and urban surface temperature (Weng et al. 2004), we regress MODIS LST on NDVI:

$$LST_i = a + b \cdot NDVI_i + e_i,$$

where the standardised residual e_i is used to represent local thermal anomaly net of vegetation effects. Grid-level anomalies are mapped to pedestrian network edges using midpoint matching. The effective heat exposure for edge e on day t is represented conceptually as:

$$H_{\text{eff}}(e, t) = H_t + \alpha \cdot S_e,$$

where α controls the contribution of local spatial anomaly to the edge-level heat exposure score.

Heat-Conditioned Walkability Penalty

To evaluate the accessibility consequences of high-heat conditions, we apply a scenario-based walking penalty to the network. The baseline network assumes standard travel time without heat-related impedance. The heat-conditioned network increases edge travel time as a monotonic function of effective heat exposure:

$$\text{TT}_{\text{heat}}(e, t) = \text{TT}_{\text{base}}(e) \cdot \phi(H_{\text{eff}}(e, t)),$$

where $\phi(\cdot)$ is a heat penalty multiplier.

Because the behavioural magnitude of heat-induced walking deterrence is uncertain and context-dependent, we implement three sensitivity scenarios: Conservative, Medium, and Aggressive. The Medium scenario is used as the primary case, while the Conservative and Aggressive scenarios provide lower- and upper-bound sensitivity checks. This design enables us to examine whether the direction and spatial structure of accessibility loss are robust across plausible penalty assumptions.

For each origin grid cell and each POI category, we compare baseline accessibility with heat-conditioned accessibility. Three core indicators are derived:

$$\Delta A = A_{\text{base}} - A_{\text{heat}},$$

$$\text{RelLoss} = \frac{\Delta A}{A_{\text{base}}},$$

$$\text{Burden} = \Delta A \times \text{Population}.$$

These measures capture absolute service loss, relative service loss, and population-weighted accessibility burden, respectively.

Behavioural Corroboration and Equity Model

We use geotagged Weibo activity records to examine whether observed urban behaviour shows patterns consistent with the modelled effects of high-heat conditions. Two forms of behavioural corroboration are conducted. First, we compare temporal activity shares between high-heat days and reference days, focusing on shifts in midday and evening activity. Second, at the 2 km grid scale, we calculate Spearman rank correlations between predicted accessibility loss and observed contraction in activity intensity.

For the equity analysis, SES is operationalised using VIIRS nighttime light intensity as a spatial proxy for local economic activity and urban development intensity. We estimate a pooled

regression model to examine whether heat-related accessibility loss varies systematically across socioeconomic contexts:

$$\text{RelLoss} \sim \text{HeatExp} + \text{SES} + A_{\text{base}} + \log(\text{Population}) + \text{HeatExp} \times \text{SES} + \text{district FE} + \text{year FE}.$$

HC1 robust standard errors are used, and residual Moran’s I is calculated to diagnose remaining spatial dependence. The interaction term $\text{HeatExp} \times \text{SES}$ is of primary interest because it indicates whether heat-related accessibility contraction differs across socioeconomic conditions.

Preliminary Findings

Accessibility Loss under High-Heat Conditions

Both 2023 and 2024 exhibit meaningful accessibility contraction under the Medium penalty scenario (*Table 1*). Mean relative service loss is 0.176 in 2023 and 0.164 in 2024. The share of populated grid cells experiencing positive accessibility loss reaches 13.44% in 2023 and 12.65% in 2024. Population-weighted accessibility burden is estimated at 4.29 million in 2023 and 4.15 million in 2024. Sensitivity analysis shows that the estimated mean loss varies from 0.100 to 0.235 in 2023 and from 0.093 to 0.221 in 2024 across Conservative and Aggressive penalty settings.

Among the five service groups, leisure-related services show the highest proportional accessibility loss, whereas food-related services contribute the largest absolute accessibility burden. These patterns suggest that high-heat exposure does not uniformly affect all dimensions of daily urban access.

Indicator	2023	2024
Mean RelLoss (Medium)	0.176	0.164
Affected populated grid share	13.44%	12.65%
Population-weighted burden (M)	4.29	4.15
Mean RelLoss (Conservative)	0.100	0.093
Mean RelLoss (Aggressive)	0.235	0.221

Table 1: Core accessibility loss indicators under heat-conditioned walkability scenarios.

Behavioural Evidence from Geotagged Weibo Activity

Behavioural results show a consistent temporal redistribution of observed urban activity under high-heat conditions. Midday activity share decreases by 1.16 percentage points in 2023 and 0.97 percentage points in 2024, while evening activity share increases by 1.48 percentage points in 2023 and 0.88 percentage points in 2024. This pattern is consistent with a time-window compression mechanism, in which people shift activity away from thermally stressful daytime periods.

Spatial corroboration provides additional support. At the 2 km grid level, the Spearman correlation between predicted accessibility loss and observed activity contraction is positive and statistically significant: $\rho = 0.182$ ($p = 0.0014$) in 2023 and $\rho = 0.161$ ($p = 0.0028$) in 2024. Although social media records cannot provide a complete representation of total urban mobility, these find-

ings offer independent behavioural evidence that the heat-conditioned accessibility model captures meaningful spatial tendencies.

Socioeconomic Heterogeneity in Accessibility Loss

The pooled equity model indicates a statistically significant interaction between heat exposure and SES under all three penalty scenarios (Table 2). In the Medium scenario, the interaction coefficient is $\beta = -0.0175$ ($p = 0.0015$). The negative sign suggests that higher-SES areas, proxied by stronger nighttime light intensity, exhibit larger relative accessibility loss after controlling for baseline accessibility, population, district fixed effects, and year fixed effects.

This result should not be interpreted as a simple reversal of environmental disadvantage. Instead, it likely reflects a ceiling effect: areas with higher baseline service accessibility may exhibit larger proportional losses once high-heat penalties are introduced, whereas lower-accessibility areas may have less nominal access available to lose in relative terms. The result therefore highlights that climate-related accessibility inequity is not adequately captured by static proximity measures alone and requires careful interpretation of both baseline access and incremental heat-related degradation.

Scenario	Interaction term	Coefficient β	p -value
Conservative	HeatExp \times SES	-0.0140	0.0042
Medium	HeatExp \times SES	-0.0175	0.0015
Aggressive	HeatExp \times SES	-0.0174	0.0030

Table 2: Pooled equity model results for the interaction between heat exposure and socioeconomic status.

Figure 2: Composite visualisation of heat-conditioned accessibility loss across penalty scenarios and service types.

Limitations and Future Work

This short paper reports preliminary findings and is subject to several limitations. First, the current heat exposure representation operates at mesoscale rather than pedestrian scale. ERA5-Land captures city-wide temporal thermal variation, while MODIS LST provides intra-urban surface thermal anomaly at a coarser spatial resolution. Together they represent background thermal stress rather than direct human-perceived outdoor thermal comfort. Street-level heterogeneity associated with building morphology, pavement materials, canopy cover, and shade is not explicitly modelled in the current version.

Second, VIIRS nighttime lights provide only a preliminary proxy for socioeconomic status. Although useful for city-wide comparative analysis, they cannot fully represent multidimensional socioeconomic vulnerability. Future work should incorporate richer demographic and socioeconomic data to better distinguish between baseline service inequality and heat-amplified accessibility inequality.

Third, geotagged Weibo records are used here as behavioural corroboration rather than as a complete mobility census. Social media activity may be affected by platform bias, user demographics, and uneven reporting intensity. Future journal-level extensions could incorporate more direct population activity indicators or commercial mobility datasets to strengthen behavioural validation.

These limitations also define the next stage of the research. The journal extension will refine the framework toward pedestrian-scale thermal accessibility modelling, integrate more explicit shade or microclimate information, improve behavioural validation, and develop a stronger equity interpretation of heat-conditioned service access.

Conclusion

Proximity alone is not sufficient for evaluating meaningful accessibility in climate-stressed cities. This study shows that high-heat conditions can systematically reduce effective walk-based access to urban services, that observed urban activity patterns display behavioural shifts consistent with this contraction, and that accessibility losses vary across socioeconomic contexts. By integrating environmental exposure signals, network-based accessibility assessment, behavioural corroboration, and equity analysis, the proposed framework provides a reproducible approach for reassessing the 15-minute city under heat stress.

As a short conference paper, this study establishes the core logic and preliminary evidence for heat-conditioned accessibility loss. Its findings suggest that climate-resilient urban planning should move beyond static geometric proximity and consider whether daily services remain functionally accessible under increasingly frequent extreme-heat conditions.

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